

MEDICAL WASTE: MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES

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Abstract: *The article discusses some issues of medical waste generation in Azerbaijan, which belong to the category of hazardous waste. In particular, it says that the waste from medical institutions contains dangerous microorganisms, toxic drugs, and is radiologically dangerous. The issues of the scale and accounting of medical waste are also being considered. The article provides a brief overview of undesirable situations of the impact of medical waste pollution on public health. It is proposed to take a more responsible approach to the disposal of all medical waste, even if it is not considered particularly dangerous. In order to reduce the risks of human infection, the spread of infections and the occurrence of epidemics, it is important to properly sort and dispose of medical waste.*

Key words: *medical waste, hazardous waste, risks of contamination by medical waste, accounting for medical waste, medical waste disposal, epidemic.*

All waste generated in the process of human existence is divided into consumer waste and production waste according to the type of origin. In general, since the emergence of people, along with other problems, there has been a waste problem. Waste is a substance or object that has lost its consumer properties as a result of human activity. This waste can be recycled. In addition, it can be disposed of or buried. Waste is classified according to its origin and degree of danger. The amount of waste has increased rapidly in the past century. Such an increase in production and consumption waste has become an important problem of large cities and large industrial sectors. In general, all waste has a negative impact on the environment.

Types of medical waste

Medical waste is divided into the following types:

- infectious waste;
- pathological-anatomical waste;
- sharps waste;
- chemical waste;
- pharmaceutical waste;
- radioactive waste;
- household waste.

Appropriate measures need to be taken to ensure the safe and sustainable management of medical waste. These measures can help prevent the negative impacts of waste on the environment and living things.

Medical waste is all waste generated during pharmaceutical and medical research activities. These include various accessories used in medical activities - gloves, needles, swabs, etc., various liquids and cotton products, as well as expired medicines. These items can accumulate a large number of harmful microorganisms. Therefore, these wastes pose a potential hazard. Medical waste is divided into five hazard classes:

- A - epidemiologically safe;
- B - epidemiologically dangerous;
- C - extremely dangerous;
- D - toxicologically dangerous;
- E - radioactive.

Statistical characteristics.

Production and consumption waste - substances or objects that are generated, produced, intended for production or consumption in the process of production, performance of work, provision of services or consumption, or are subject to production or disposal in accordance with the Law. Waste does not include subsoil used in accordance with the legislation of our State, as well as surface and bedrock that must be used in accordance with the Law No. 707 "On Subsoil" dated April 27, 1998.

On average, 350 kilograms of waste fall on a resident of our capital per year. This is not a small number. This figure is for the city of Baku. What about our Republic? Other cities? Other countries? If we add up the figures generated here, we will get a huge amount. For example, in Japan, more than 50 million tons of household waste are generated per year. At the same time, the amount of industrial waste is eight times more than this [1].

According to the Statistical Committee, 4400.0 thousand tons of waste were generated in Azerbaijan in 2024. This is approximately 7% more than in the previous year. 70% of them were solid household waste. The remaining figure was various types of waste generated by the activities of enterprises [7].

Medical waste is classified as hazardous waste. The share of medical waste in the total amount of waste is about 3%. Only a short overview of the risks suggests that the waste from medical institutions contains dangerous microorganisms, toxic drugs, and is radiologically dangerous. Therefore, the issue of their disposal is being taken very seriously all over the world.

An assessment of waste data from around the world shows that hospitals produce about 0.5 kg of garbage per hospital bed per day. However, this figure and the basic composition of waste vary greatly depending on local conditions.

For example, higher-income countries produce much more waste and plastic, which often accounts for more than half of all medical waste. Because of this huge difference, there is no single best solution for medical waste management. Therefore, each country has its own expert staff dealing with the problem in local realities.

For a long time, there was no accounting system for medical waste in Azerbaijan. Direct work on this issue has been underway since about 2000, and much has already been done, but much remains to be done.

The danger of medical waste.

Of the 302,600 tons of solid waste generated in 2024, 80.5% were transported to landfills for disposal. Approximately 20% of this was used to generate electricity. Thus, more than 230 million kWh of electricity was generated from them. This is 4% more than the previous year [7].

22.2% of industrial waste in 2023 was used as raw materials in enterprises in all sectors of the economy. Approximately 15% was sold within the country.

In 2024, more than 260,000 tons of hazardous waste were generated. This accounted for 6% of the total amount of waste. Approximately 72% of waste belongs to mining enterprises.

Patients suffering from various infectious diseases have to undergo many medical procedures. And there are a lot of invasive ones among them. Injections, ivs, surgical intervention, research – for example, gastroscopy, and so on, which forms a considerable number of disposable instruments and materials contaminated with biological fluids – dressing, hygienic and others. All this can cause infection of medical staff, which means it has a high degree of epidemiological danger. There are 20 billion injections per year in the world. Over the past 25 years, about 150 new medical institutions have appeared in Azerbaijan. These are both public and private. However, reliable figures on medical waste cannot be found. At the same time, the scale is easy to imagine.

Medical waste and by-products can also lead to other risks, such as:

- injuries caused by sharp objects;
- poisoning and environmental pollution as a result of the release of medicines, in particular antibiotics and cytotoxic drugs;
- poisoning and pollution of the environment by sewage;

poisoning and pollution of the environment by toxic elements or compounds such as mercury or dioxins released during waste incineration.

Experience and practice.

The World Health Organization estimates that twenty-one million hepatitis B virus (HBV) infections, two million hepatitis C virus infections and 260,000 HIV infections occur worldwide on average per year as a result of injections with contaminated syringes. And Kyrgyzstan is no exception to this sad statistic.

In developing countries, additional dangers arise from the fact that people are rummaging through garbage in waste disposal sites, that is, in landfills. People who handle waste are at immediate risk of injury as a result of needle pricks and exposure to toxic and infectious materials.

There are more depressing cases. In June 2000, six children were diagnosed with a mild form of smallpox after they played with glass vials containing expired smallpox vaccine in a landfill in one of the Russian cities. The outbreak was localized, but everything could have an unpredictable outcome. Therefore, it is very important that medical waste is safe at the final stage when it is placed in landfills and does not pose a danger to both the environment and the public.

Actions.

Health care activities are aimed at protecting and improving public health. As a result of this activity, various types of waste are generated. Medical waste is considered one of the most hazardous types of waste. The concept of medical waste is included in the official document "On the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal" [2]. Here, the term "medical waste" is defined as "waste generated as a result of medical care for patients in hospitals, clinics and outpatient clinics".

The potential hazards of medical waste for the environment and people living and working in it can be divided into the following risks:

- risk of physical injury from sharp objects;
- risk of toxic contamination from chemical disinfection of medical waste;
- risk of infectious contamination from contact with contaminated material;
- risk of radioactive contamination from contact with radioactive waste;
- environmental risk associated with the release and spread of such waste into the environment.

The use of radiation sources in medical and other devices is widespread in our country. Naturally, waste is generated in an appropriate amount. And it's not safe. Serious incidents were reported in Brazil in 1988. In this country, four people died and about thirty suffered serious radiation burns. In Mexico and Morocco in 1983, in Algeria in 1978 and in Mexico in 1962. In our republic, the issue of radiological waste disposal has not been fully resolved, despite the work done.

In our republic, over 25 years of work in this area, many issues have been resolved. The waste separation process has been established, protocols for each class have been developed, the practice of disinfection with toxic chlorine is no longer used, many hospitals use modern plastic disinfection techniques and send it not to landfill, to poison the environment, but for recycling. However, there is still no clear, well-established system for the disposal of chemical waste and the serious risks caused by interaction with mercury-containing material have not been prevented. There are a lot of problems.

The process of implementing a good medical waste management system is complicated. It entails not only an assessment of waste categories and existing practices that have already been implemented in Azerbaijan, but also the selection of waste disposal options, the development of a waste management plan, the adoption of institutional policies and guidelines, the creation of a waste management organization, the allocation of human and financial resources, the implementation of plans in accordance with established deadlines, and also, the implementation of a program of periodic training, monitoring, evaluation and continuous improvement of the system.

Work in this direction should be carried out continuously, because science is developing, new technologies are coming, and the situation is changing. And decision makers must see and understand the priority of this problem.

Minimizing the risks of infection.

It is necessary to take responsibility for the disposal of all medical waste, even if it is not considered particularly dangerous. In order to reduce the risks of human infection, the spread of infections and the occurrence of epidemics, it is important to properly sort and dispose of medical waste. Medical personnel are advised to use a specially designed video course that provides detailed information about the categories of medical waste and how to dispose of it.

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